

THE EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF PERFORMANCE OF PULTRUDED ROD COMPOSITE STRUTS IN COMPRESSION

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The Composites Centre
for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

Motivation & Aim

MOTIVATION

- Within NextCOMP we have a need to test pultruded rod specimens.
- For 0.8 mm diameter pultruded rods, we have developed a 'cradle' test.
- For rods of larger diameter (6 mm), the cradle becomes large and debonding of rod is a problem.
- Direct compression tests can be susceptible to premature failure.

CONCEPT

- Eccentricity (e) promotes bending.
- Stresses at load introduction (via endcap) can be relatively small
- Specimen at the strut centre is subjected to an axial force (F) and a bending moment of $F(e + \delta)$ where δ is deflection from initial strut centre line.
- The maximum compressive strain will be the summation of the axial and bending strains.
- Not new!

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To investigate an eccentric buckling test methodology to evaluate the compressive performance of large diameter pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites.

- Compressive failure strain
- Compressive modulus

Specimens

SPECIMEN MATERIAL

- EasyComposite Pultruded Rod (ECPR) 6 mm diameter, 300 mm long carbon fibre/epoxy rods, $v_f = \sim 33\%$.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Instrumentation

Three strain gauges separated by 120° at mid-length position

Nominal max compressive strain location

Speckle pattern for DIC

Assembled test specimen

Engraved mark for bonding alignment-

Specimen bonding region

Endcap design

Experimental procedure & data reduction

TEST PROCEDURE

- Instron 1341 test machine fitted with a 5 kN axial loadcell.
- Displacement-control at a constant crosshead speed of 3 mm/min until failure.
- Load and applied displacement measured by test machine.
- Lateral displacement measured by DIC.
- Strains measured from strain gauges and DIC.

Test setup

DATA REDUCTION - I

Measure β and γ :

Setting A as the max bending strain and C as the axial strain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= A \sin(\alpha) + C \\ \varepsilon_2 &= A \sin(\alpha + \beta) + C \\ \varepsilon_3 &= A \sin(\alpha + \gamma) + C \end{aligned} \right\} \text{Solve for } A, C \text{ and } \alpha$$

Assumes plane sections remain plane

DATA REDUCTION - II

****Assumes linear elastic material****

$$\sigma_{axial} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2}$$

$$\max \sigma_{bending} = \pm \frac{32F(e + \delta)}{\pi D^3}$$

$$\max \sigma_{compressive} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2} - \frac{32F(e + \delta)}{\pi D^3}$$

Results and discussion

FAILURE VIDEO

EXPERIMENTAL LOAD-DISPLACEMENT

EXPERIMENTAL LOAD-DISPLACEMENT

STRAIN GAUGE POSITIONS

From X-ray CT
 $\beta = 125.45^\circ$
 $\gamma = 246.85^\circ$

MAX. COMPRESSIVE STRESS VS MAX. COMPRESSIVE STRAIN

MAX. COMPRESSIVE STRESS VS MAX. COMPRESSIVE STRAIN

- Compressive modulus (87.3 ± 3.0 GPa), taken from strain range from -0.002 to -0.005.
- Good agreement with tensile elastic modulus (88 ± 0.2 GPa).
- Compressive strain at strut failure is -0.0145 ± 0.001 **BUT failure is tensile**
- Very linear up to failure of the strut
- But remember: assumed linear elastic material to retrieve max compression stress.
- Could this apparent linear relationship be misleading?

FE PREDICTED MAX. STRESS VERSUS MAX. STRAIN

$$\max \sigma_{compressive} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2} - \frac{32F(e + \delta)}{\pi D^3}$$

FE PREDICTED MAX. STRESS VERSUS MAX. STRAIN

$$\max \sigma_{compressive} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2} - \frac{32F(e + \delta)}{\pi D^3}$$

Axial stress vs axial strain

- Initially linear.
- Axial modulus (85.5 ± 1.3 GPa), taken from strain range from 0-0.0001 (small strains!).
- Again, good agreement with tensile elastic modulus (88 ± 0.2 GPa).
- What is causing the non-linearity?

FE PREDICTED AXIAL STRESS VERSUS AXIAL STRAIN I

$$\sigma_{axial} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2}$$

FE PREDICTED AXIAL STRESS VERSUS AXIAL STRAIN II

$$\sigma_{axial} = -\frac{4F}{\pi D^2}$$

Axial stress vs axial strain

- Shape is indicative of a softening behaviour
- Why does this occur?
- Explanation.....

SOURCE OF NON-LINEARITY IN AXIAL STRESS-STRAIN

Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

- We have explored an eccentric buckling test methodology to investigate compressive performance of 6 mm diameter pultruded rods.
- The compressive elastic modulus (87.3 ± 3.0 GPa) was in good agreement with tensile elastic modulus of 88 ± 0.18 GPa.
- The compressive strain at rod failure (-0.0145 ± 0.0010)
- BUT rod failure initiated on the tensile side and will be investigated further (strain gradient effect?).

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<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

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